

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF A LAMINATED BASALT COMPOSITE PLATE SUBJECTED TO BLAST LOAD

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ABSTRACT

The use of the advanced laminated composites is become more important in the structures of many engineering applications such as space stations, aerospace vehicles, automotives and marine structures. Also, with the increasing use of recent composite material structures in the military applications, non-linear dynamic analysis of these materials subjected to blast loads resulting from fuel and nuclear explosions, and the rush of sonic boom are becoming increasingly more significant. The nonlinear dynamic response of a blast loaded laminated basalt composite plate has been investigated experimentally and numerically. The laminated basalt composite plate is fully-clamped at all edges. For numerical analyses, the equations of motion for the plate are derived by the use of the virtual work principle. Approximate solutions are assumed for the space domain and substituted into the equations of motion. Then the Galerkin Method is used to obtain the nonlinear differential equations in the time domain. The Newmark Method is applied to solve the system of coupled nonlinear equations by writing a computer code in MATLAB. On the experimental side of the study, tests have been carried out on the laminated basalt composite plates, in sixteen layers of stacking sequences and obtained by infusion, with fully-clamped edges for blast loads. The approximate-numerical and ANSYS results are compared with the experimental ones. We have obtained a good agreement for the specific points.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, advanced laminated composites are becoming more important structural components and the use of them increasing day by day in many engineering applications such as pace stations, aerospace vehicles, automotives and marine structures [1]. Also, with the increasing use of recent composite material structures in the military applications, non-linear dynamic analysis of these

materials subjected to blast loads resulting from fuel and nuclear explosions, and the rush of sonic boom are becoming increasingly more significant.

One of the recent promising materials for the fabrication of the advanced composite materials is basalt fiber. Composites reinforced with basalt fibers have superior properties over the other composites such as; recyclable, safer even in the factory, better elastic modulus than fiberglass, ten times better electrical insulator than glass fibers, low cost, having better impact strength, protecting from nuclear radiation. Moreover, they do not harbour mold, mildew or bacteria. No UV treatments are needed. They will not ignite easily with the right resins. Basalt fibers do not shatter like carbon fibers and they are resistant to blast load. Lastly, basalt fiber reinforced composites have good mechanical properties especially at high temperature.

Over these many good properties, its possible applications have not been investigated completely yet. New basalt fibre composite applications could be widely used in near future due to the potential low cost of this material. Lopresto et al. [2] have investigated the mechanical characterization of basalt fiber reinforced plastic. They found that basalt composite showed 35-42% higher Young's modulus as well as better compressive strength and flexural behavior, while a higher tensile strength was found for glass fibers. Basalt fiber reinforced poly (butylene succinate) composites are fabricated by Zhang et al. [3]. They investigated the effects of the basalt fiber on the the composites' mechanical and thermal properties, and also found that using of basalt fibers as reinforcement in a natural fiber composite can significantly improve the mechanical properties and performance of polymer matrix resins. Elsanadedy et al. [4] used a new type basalt-based textile in order to strength the material. Colombo et al. [5] have showed the experimental results of several static and fatigue tests of the new basalt fibre reinforced composites. S.Baştürk et al. [1] have proposed an analytical model for predicting the deflection of laminated basalt composite plates under dynamic blast loads. They showed that using basalt composite plates may well be more preferable or might at least provide a valuable alternative for glass composite structures.

In this study, numerical and experimental analysis of laminated basalt composite plates have been investigated and compared. For numerical analyses, the equations of motion for the plate are derived by the use of the virtual work principle. Approximate solutions are assumed for the space domain and substituted into the equations of motion. Then the Galerkin Method is used to obtain the nonlinear differential equations in the time domain. The Newmark Method is applied to solve the system of coupled nonlinear equations. ANSYS commercial finite element software is also used to compare the results. On the experimental side of the study, tests have been carried out on the laminated basalt composite plates, in sixteen layers of stacking sequences and obtained by infusion, with fully-clamped edges for blast loads. The results of theoretical and numerical methods are compared with the experimental results. Theoretical and numerical results are in a good agreement.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSES

A laminated basalt composite plate subjected to blast load is considered. The rectangular plate with the length a , the width b , and the thickness h , which is clamped by all edges is depicted in Fig. 1. The Cartesian axes are used in the derivation.

Figure 1: Laminated basalt composite.

Kazancı and Mecitoğlu [6] have studied nonlinear damped vibrations of such kind of laminated composite plate subjected to blast load. They have obtained the nonlinear dynamic equations of a laminated composite plate in terms of mid-plane displacements, using the constitutive equations and the strain-displacement relations in the virtual work and applying the variational principles, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{11}u^0 + L_{12}v^0 + L_{13}w^0 + N_1(w^0) + d_1\dot{u}^0 + \bar{m}\ddot{u}^0 - q_x &= 0 \\ L_{21}u^0 + L_{22}v^0 + L_{23}w^0 + N_2(w^0) + d_2\dot{v}^0 + \bar{m}\ddot{v}^0 - q_y &= 0 \\ L_{31}u^0 + L_{32}v^0 + L_{33}w^0 + N_3(u^0, v^0, w^0) + d_3\dot{w}^0 + \bar{m}\ddot{w}^0 - q_z &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here, L_{ij} and N_i are linear and nonlinear operators. \bar{m} is the mass of unit area of the mid-plane, where q_x , q_y and q_z are the load vectors in the axes directions, while d_1 , d_2 and d_3 denote the viscous damping coefficients in the x, y and z directions, respectively. However, damping effects are neglected for this study by taking damping coefficients zero. The explicit expressions of the operators can be found at the Appendix of [6]. The boundary conditions are considered as all edges are clamped and given as:

$$\begin{aligned} u^0(0, y, t) = u^0(a, y, t) = u^0(x, 0, t) = u^0(x, b, t) &= 0 \quad , \\ \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x}(0, y, t) = \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x}(a, y, t) = \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y}(x, 0, t) = \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y}(x, b, t) &= 0 \\ v^0(0, y, t) = v^0(a, y, t) = v^0(x, 0, t) = v^0(x, b, t) &= 0 \quad , \\ \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x}(0, y, t) = \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x}(a, y, t) = \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y}(x, 0, t) = \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y}(x, b, t) &= 0 \\ w^0(0, y, t) = w^0(a, y, t) = w^0(x, 0, t) = w^0(x, b, t) &= 0 \quad , \\ \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x}(0, y, t) = \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x}(a, y, t) = \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y}(x, 0, t) = \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y}(x, b, t) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and initial conditions are given by

$$\begin{aligned} u^0(x, y, 0) = 0, \quad v^0(x, y, 0) = 0, \quad w^0(x, y, 0) = 0, \\ \dot{u}^0(x, y, 0) = 0, \quad \dot{v}^0(x, y, 0) = 0, \quad \dot{w}^0(x, y, 0) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

If the blast source is distant enough from the plate, the blast pressure can be described in terms of the Friedlander exponential decay equation as

$$P(t) = p_m(1 - t/t_p)e^{-\alpha t/t_p} \quad (4)$$

where the negative phase of the blast is included. Here p_m is peak pressure, t_p is positive phase duration and α is waveform parameter (Fig.2).

Figure 2: Exponential blast loading.

2 PRODUCTION OF THE SPECIMENS

A basalt fiber reinforced polymer matrix laminated plate, 400mm x 400mm, were obtained by resin infusion technology. Basalt dry fabrics - 200 g/m², plain weave (warp 10F/10 mm, weft 10F/10 mm), tex 100, from ZLBM (De) - were overlapped and impregnated through infusion by an epoxy matrix (Becor I-SX10 + hardener SX10M). Then, the specimen was covered with the peel ply and the plastic bag in which the vacuum was done. The curing stage at room temperature and at a vacuum level of -990 mbar was performed for 24 hours. The following stacking sequence was obtained: (0,90)_n n=16, and t = 2.5 mm; V_f = 50%. On the other hand, specimens for coupon tests of tension, compression and shear to obtain the mechanical properties were also manufactured. Standards of ASTM D638, ASTM D695 and ASTM D3518 were used for tension, compression and shear properties, respectively. Dimensioning of coupons also depends on these standards.

Figure 3: Resin infusion apparatus.

3 EXPERIMENTS

The experimental side of the study was investigated by simulating an environment and setting up a testing mechanism. The air blast load test can be carried out on a laminated basalt plate as a two stage procedure. First, transient pressure measurement on a plexiglass model plate and defining the distribution of pressure on the plate have been done. Then, strain measurement has been performed on laminated basalt composite plate. The overview of experimental set-up is shown in Figure 4. After the pressure is measured with plexiglass model, the basalt plate is replaced between the steel frames instead of plexiglass model for the measurement of strain values.

Figure 4: The overview of experimental set-up.

This procedure is preferred because of the type of pressure sensors that were used. The disadvantage of this sensor is that a mounting hole must be prepared on the plate. To avoid the stress concentrations around these holes on basalt plate, the conducted testing procedure is more feasible.

The air compressor is used for storing the pressurized air from outside air into pressure tank. The compressor can pump the air up to 40 bar into pressure tank. The pressure tank has the capacity about 500 litres of pressurized air. The connection between the regulator and the shock tube is provided by a pressure resistant hose. The hose is about 10 meter long and resistant up to 256 bar. PCB 111A26 piezoelectric quartz miniature pressure sensors and Vishay C2A-06-125LT-350 strain gage 0°-90° rosettes were used for measuring. IMC C-Series CS-7008-N data acquisition device that has 8 channels and 100 kHz sampling rate was used for collecting data.

Membranes are thin structures and are used in shock tube tests. Its function is to separate the shock tube into two parts: the high pressure part and low pressure part. The membrane keeps the air in the high pressure part until it is ruptured. When the membrane is ruptured, the pressurized air passes through the low pressure part with a very high speed. After that, the air hits the plate, because the plate acts like a barrier for the high speed air. In this study, selection of the membrane material is very important. The burst pressure that is obtained by the rupture of membrane, must be nearly the same in each burst test. Because, the measurement of pressure values and the measurement of strain values are separated from each other and they are not measured at the same time and by using on the same tested plate. After doing some burst tests for membrane selection, it is decided to use Mylar® polyester film with a thickness of 0.19 mm is chosen for the membrane. Figure 5 shows the rupture of one polyester membrane at about 6 bar. Different views of test set-up excluding compressor and pressure tank is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: The rupture of polyester film.

Figure 6: The views of test set-up.

The pressure distribution on the 400x400 mm plexiglass plate has been assumed to be uniform after doing tens of repeated tests at 17 different selected points on the model plate. The affected area is 300x300 mm due to two 5 mm wide hollow rectangular steel frames as seen in Figure 6. So, a 300x300 mm clamped laminated basalt composite plate (shown in Fig.1) has been simulated.

Friedlander decay function can express the experimental results of air blast load as shown in Equation 4 and the load can be vary exponentially in time. The blast load is expanded in Fourier series and only the first term is chosen. p_m is the peak pressure, t_p is positive phase duration, and ϕ is a waveform parameter. Figure 7 shows the history of idealized experimental uniform blast pressure in time.

Figure 7: Idealized experimental uniform blast pressure in time.

3 NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

First of all, the structural model presented in this paper was validated with ANSYS finite element software results. Properties of the 16 layered specimens used in the analyses are given in Table 1.

Modulus of Elasticity ($E_1=E_2$) (GPa)	Shear Modulus G_{12} (GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν	Density ρ (kg/m^3)	Total thickness (mm)
23.498	9.037	0.11	2320	2.5

Table 1: Properties of the specimens.

The dimensions of the plate are $a=b=0.30$ m and, $h=2.5(10^{-3})$ m. (see Table 1). The analyses are performed for the uniform blast pressure. The maximum blast pressure is taken to be 28150 Pa for the plate and all edges are clamped. The other parameters of the Friedländer function given in Eq. (4) are chosen as $\alpha=0.35$ and $t_p=0.001$ s. The displacement (w/h)-time histories of the plate center obtained with ANSYS and approximate-numerical method are compared in Figure 8 for the center of the plate and for the point of $a/4, b/4$ for 20 ms. As seen from the figure 8, approximate-numerical results are almost the same especially for the strong blast regime.

Figure 8: Comparison of the deflections (w/h).

Figure 9 shows the comparison of the microstrains for ANSYS results and for 3 test specimens for the center of the plates. It can be said that ANSYS results and the experimental results are compatible especially for the strong blast regime as is for Figure 8.

Figure 9: Microstrain comparisons of the 3 test specimens and ANSYS results. ($x=a/2$, $y=b/2$)

It has been seen from Figure 10 that the comparison of the microstrains for ANSYS results and for 3 test specimens for the point of $a/4$ and $b/4$. Up to 2 ms, experimental results and ANSYS results are in a good agreement. However, there is a discrepancy after this moment. It should be mentioned that damping effects are neglected in theory and ANSYS while there was a damping effect for the tests.

Figure 10: Microstrain comparisons of the 3 test specimens and ANSYS results ($x=a/4$, $y=b/4$).

In Figure 11, microstrain results are compared by performing three different tests for two points on the plate's bottom surface. Center points' strain values are greater than the other point, as expected. Frequencies are obtained nearly the same for three different experiments. These results indicate that the values obtained from the tests should be correct.

Figure 11: Microstrain comparisons of several tests with the same specimens from different points.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, numerical and experimental analysis of laminated basalt composite plates have been investigated and compared. For numerical analyses, the equations of motion for the plate are derived by the use of the virtual work principle. Approximate solutions are assumed for the space domain and substituted into the equations of motion. Then the Galerkin Method is used to obtain the nonlinear differential equations in the time domain. The Newmark Method is applied to solve the system of coupled nonlinear equations by writing a computer code in MATLAB. On the experimental side of the study, tests have been carried out on the laminated basalt composite plates, in sixteen layers of stacking sequences and obtained by infusion, with fully-clamped edges for blast loads. The approximate-numerical and ANSYS results are compared with the experimental ones. Theoretical and numerical results are in a good agreement.

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